

The Main Forms of the Catalytic Action*

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Catalysis is the main means for accomplishing chemical transformations in nature and in human practical activities. Elucidation of the regularities of the catalytic action is one of the most important problems in chemical science. The solution of this problem presents a great difficulty since it requires, as a rule, investigation of the dynamics of chemical interaction, in rather complicated chemical systems. Therefore, the development of the theory of catalysis proceeds via the route of particular generalizations. Separate theoretical concepts exist which depict the peculiarities of homogeneous, heterogeneous and enzymic catalysis. This is a result of different investigation on systems which require specific experimental methods and theoretical approaches. Nevertheless, the nature of the phenomenon is similar in all these fields of catalysis.

In the present paper an attempt has been made to formulate this general nature of the catalytic action of all types of catalysts.

General Factors determining the Reaction Rate

IN chemical reactions, the formation of a new compound is connected with breaking of certain bonds in initial compounds. This necessitates overcoming a certain energy barrier in reaction route, i. e. requires an energy of activation. For many thermodynamically permitted reactions, the activation energy is so high that the reaction rate is not appreciable. It is to be noted, however, that the value of activation energy, when it can be estimated, is considerably smaller than the sum of energies required for breaking bonds, i. e., in reaction route a portion of energy needed for breaking old bonds is compensated by the energy released during formation of new bonds [Fig. 1].

Fig. 1. The compensation degree of old bond breaking energy along the reaction route.

This degree of compensation, however, is not the same for all reactions. For example, for the most simplified reactions of molecules with a hydrogen atom or radical the compensation degree reaches 95 percent and more whereas in reactions between saturated molecules, the compensation is usually much smaller, and due to a low reaction rate it is very difficult to estimate its value in such cases.

Реакция	E ккал/моль	ΣD _i ккал/моль	Н %
H + Cl ₂ → HCl + Cl	2	57	96
H + Br ₂ → HBr + Br	1,2	45	97
H + D ₂ → HD + D	6,5	105	94
H + CH ₃ CHO → H ₂ + CH ₃ CO	6	85	93
H + C ₂ H ₆ → H ₂ + C ₂ H ₅	9,5	98	90
OH + CH ₄ → H ₂ O + CH ₃	8,5	101	92
OH + CH ₃ CHO → H ₂ O + CH ₃ CO	4,0	85	95

Table 1. Calculation of the compensation degree for radical reactions.

Of late, a considerable amount of work has been done on the kinetic characteristics of gas- and liquid-phase reactions. But unfortunately, all these reactions involved the participation of radicals. Recently the Russian School has succeeded in obtaining the kinetic characteristics of about 40 reactions between molecules [Fig. 2]. It has been observed that the degree of compensation in these reactions is much less (70 percent) compared to those involving radicals (95 percent). Thus, the interaction between the species of a non-radical nature does not provide any significant compensation of energy of breaking of old bonds and, therefore, requires overcoming a high energy barrier and cannot proceed at a marked rate.

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Fig. 2. Distribution of a compensation degree. 1—reactions incorporating radicals, 2—reactions between molecules.

In the past years, several attempts have been made to estimate a compensation degree depending on certain characteristics of electron structure of reactants and its variations during reaction process. As it was impossible to obtain quantitative estimates, various qualitative methods have been tried and the successful rule of conservation of orbital symmetry (Woodward and Hoffmann) in the reaction route has been formulated. With the help of rule and use of a correlation diagram, it is possible to determine a product state (main or excited) which correlates by symmetry with the main state of the reactant. In the first case the reaction is a permitted one; a barrier caused by the symmetry is absent. In the second case the reaction is a forbidden one, i. e., it must overcome a certain energy barrier. Take for example, the formation of cyclobutane from ethylene Fig. [3,4]. This reaction is a forbidden one because the main stage of reactants correlates with an excited state of cyclobutene.

Other examples of 'forbidden' reactions are isotopic exchange in diatomic molecules; hydrogenation of olefins with molecular hydrogen; interaction of H_2 with N_2 halides, etc.

This qualitative method of Woodward and Hoffmann has been checked for a great number of systems, and the results obtained are in satisfactory agreement with the experimental data.

Fig. 3. The scheme of cyclization of two ethylene molecules and their symmetry planes.

Fig. 4. A correlation diagram of ethylene cyclization.

However, one should not overestimate the role of the orbital symmetry. The rule of conservation of orbital symmetry is a convenient and elegant method for estimating energy profiles of reaction routes, i. e., of a compensation degree for synchronous conversions. The authors of the method emphasize that "... the main idea of the principle is based on an undoubted statement that the higher is the degree of conservation of bonding during conversion, the easier is the reaction proceeding". In other words, the process of breaking old bonds must not go ahead of the formation of new ones. Other methods have also been suggested for estimating the facility of electron rearrangement. Among them was the reflection method proposed by Trindle, according to which the smoothness in the reaction route is characterized by conservation of the number of knots in molecular orbital.

Interstage compensation

A low degree of compensation hinders proceeding of many reactions via a synchronous mechanism.

There exists, however, one more possibility for compensation of energy of old bonds breaking. It is a well known chain mechanism. In this case a synchronous interreaction is replaced by a stage, chain one, accompanied by the formation of species at each stage which accumulate chemical reaction energy and react with reactants at the subsequent stages. These species are usually atoms, radicals and labile molecules. A high reaction rate is due to the fact that the concentration of intermediate energy-rich reactive species can be much greater than the equilibrium concentration (very often by several orders) owing to a free reaction energy. Small activation energies at each stage are caused by the compensation of the energy of breaking old bonds due to the formation of new ones. However, this compensation does not proceed in the elementary act (as opposed to concerted mechanism); it proceeds via transition of energy in a chemical form on to the subsequent stage. According to this, the chain route may be called as interstage compensation.

A lot of chemical processes of practical importance can proceed via these chain mechanisms: combustion, partial oxidation of some organic substances in a liquid phase, thermal cracking, halogenation, radical polymerization. However, this route, which might be called as an interstage compensation of energy of old bonds breaking, is possible only for a limited number of systems wherein chemical energy can be accumulated and exothermal effect is sufficiently great.

Catalysis

The conditions necessary for compensation of energy, as stated above, are not fulfilled for most cases of chemical conversions. In the absence of energy compensation the only means of effecting the conversion in such cases is through the process of catalysis.

Catalysis may be defined as the phenomenon of acceleration of chemical reactions due to an intermediate chemical interaction between reactants and another substance—catalyst—which is not incorporated into the composition of reaction products. Owing to this, a new reaction route becomes possible which provides an increased reaction rate in a certain direction. The presence of an additional species-catalyst which interacts with reactants may remove the restraints imposed by orbital symmetry conservation, may aid the conservation of bonding in the reaction route, and as a result, increase the degree of compensation. The possibility of switching the forbidden transformation into an allowed one, due to the participation of a catalyst in the active reaction complex, has been discussed in a series of studies.

Let us consider the conversion reaction of two ethylene molecules to cyclobutane which is a symmetry forbidden reaction. This reaction is forbidden due to the correlation between an antibonding orbital in ethylene molecule and a bonding orbital in cyclobutane. For this reaction to occur, reactant orbital must be occupied while orbital which correlates with an antibonding orbital of the product must be empty. From this it is possible to derive electron properties of a hypothetical catalyst which must give an electron pair to reactant orbital and trap electrons from antibonding orbital of the product. Transition metal ions with partially filled d-orbitals ideally meet these requirements.

An intermediate chemical interaction between reactants and a catalyst may proceed via either stepwise or concerted mechanism. In the former case individual stages of the catalytic process, i. e., interaction of reactants with a catalyst, separation of the reaction products from the catalyst, etc., proceed stepwise and between the end of the previous stage and the beginning of the subsequent one an equilibrium distribution of energy in intermediates

is observed. The energy profile of the reaction route is correspondingly characterized by maxima and minima [Fig. 5]. If the equilibrium energy distribution is not achieved before the beginning of the subsequent stage, the energy released during the previous stage and partially accumulated by the system may decrease the activation energy of the subsequent stage, in other words, the compensation degree may be increased due to the energy of the previous stage (Fig. 5, curve 2). This type of interstage compensation, hereinafter called interstage compensation of the second type, significantly differs from that observed in chain reaction since this compensation is within one reaction cycle and after onset of the second stage, the realization of the equilibrium energy distribution is achieved.

Fig. 5. Variations in the reaction system energy along the reaction route.

In the case of concerted or synchronous mechanism, in addition to the catalyst, all reactants are incorporated into the composition of an active complex. Only one energy maximum is retained in the reaction route [Fig 5, curve 3]. The concerted mechanism might be considered as a limiting case of interstage compensation of the second type if the period of time between the stages is shortened.

Stepwise mechanism

Oxidation reactions on oxide catalysts may serve as an example of a stepwise mechanism. In the Institute of Catalysis of the Siberian Branch of the USSR Academy of Sciences, a lot of oxidation reactions have been studied by separately measuring the rates of stages of catalyst oxidation with oxygen and its reduction with an oxidized substance under stationary conditions and by comparing them with the rate of the catalytic reaction in the presence of both components. Decreasing oxygen content on the surface results in a decrease of the rate of reduction and an increase of the oxidation rate. The stage at which the rates of reduction equal those of oxidation corresponds to the stationary state. The fact that these rates coincide with the rate of independently measured catalytic reaction is a definite proof of the stepwise mechanism.

It was found that at elevated temperatures reactions of complete oxidation of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, and many other organic substances, as well as reactions of partial oxidation of olefins, alcohols, aromatic compounds, on selective catalysts, proceed via the stage mechanism with a stepwise interaction of reactants with a catalyst. As the temperature is decreased, the deviations are observed in cases involving complete oxidation; the rate of the catalytic reaction considerably exceeds the rates of individual stages.

Increasing the number of stages leads to a decrease in the number and total energy of breaking bonds for individual stages. However, when reactants interact with a catalyst the energy of breaking old bonds is compensated by the binding energy with the catalyst, and this leads to the fact that at one of the stages the total energy of breaking bonds is of the order similar to that of synchronous conversion without participation of a catalyst.

For example, in hydrogenation of ethylene

a hydrogen bond must be broken, and a double bond in ethylene must change to a single one. A stepwise interaction can proceed via the following path:

In this case only one bond in hydrogen molecule is broken at the first stage; at the second stage a double bond in ethylene is broken, while at the third stage all bonds of reactants with a catalyst formed at the previous stages must be broken. Since they are not less by their values than the energy of breaking bonds in reactants, the situation at this stage is not facilitated as compared to synchronous transformation.

A significant effect with respect to the total value of energy of breaking bonds is achieved only in the case when division into stages results in the decrease in the reaction molecularity, as for example, in oxidation with molecular oxygen, synthesis of ammonia, hydrogenation during a stepwise addition of hydrogen atoms and in similar processes. When hydrogen is oxidized with molecular oxygen the sum of energies of breaking bonds at all stages is smaller than that for synchronous path.

Thus, with the stage mechanism, when molecularity is decreased it is possible to decrease the sum of energies of breaking bonds at all stages, and at equal compensation degree to decrease the activation energy as compared to a synchronous route. In the case when the molecularity cannot be decreased the increase of the reaction rate is possible only when a compensation degree of energy of breaking bonds is increased at the stage by the increased sum of the energies of broken bonds. The increase in the compensation degree is the most important factor of increasing the reaction rate in the major cases of catalytic action.

Concerted (associative) mechanism in catalysis

When reactions proceed via a concerted mechanism, an increase in the degree of compensation is achieved through the chemical interaction with a catalyst which can remove the restraints imposed by orbital symmetry conservation, facilitate electron transitions between reactants, aid the migration of individual atoms between reactant molecules or their fragments, facilitate reaching the optimal mutual orientation of reactants, etc.

The action of these factors is manifested in incorporation of reactants as ligand into complex metal compounds (especially transition metal compounds); in chemisorption of reactants on surfaces of metals, oxides, and other solid compounds; bonding in cavities of zeolites containing acidic groups and various cations; and probably, in the most complete form, in the reaction with enzyme active centers.

In the past years there have been a series of papers and reviews on explanation of the catalytic action in symmetry-allowed reactions like cyclization and dimerization of olefins, isomerization and disproportionation. Concerted mechanism has also been observed in reactions of catalytic oxidation on solid oxides. However, a concerted mechanism is apparently less common in hydrogenation reactions.

The most detailed study of the concerted mechanism has been performed for reactions of catalytic oxygen isotopic homoexchange. It is a known fact that on many oxide catalysts treated under vacuum, homoexchange proceeds at a high rate at very low temperature without any participation of the catalyst oxygen atoms. We can propose that a low-temperature exchange proceeds through a three- and four-atomic complex on metal cations. The orbital symmetry conservation principle suggests a tetrahedral structure of the complex with an apex at the

catalyst surface. These may be formed while joining an oxygen molecule to ion-radical O_2^- , associated with a transition metal atom and situated perpendicularly to the surface [Fig. 6]. The reaction of carbon monoxide with water vapor can serve as an example. For approximate estimation we may assume that during the reaction one π -bond in a CO molecule and bonds between hydrogen and oxygen in a water molecule are broken. The total energy of the broken bonds is equal to 282 kcal, and this explains the absence of interaction without a catalyst. With iron oxide catalyst (Fe_3O_4), conversion proceeds through the stages: carbon monoxide interacts with the catalyst-oxygen forming CO_2 , and the catalyst is reoxidized with H_2O .

Fig. 6. Structure of an active complex involved in the oxygen homomolecular exchange.

It is noteworthy that in the given case the stepwise mechanism does not decrease the reaction molecularity, and acceleration is achieved by compensation of energy of breaking of old bonds. For example, in the reduction of catalyst (the most hampered stage), the degree of compensation is found to be more than 85 percent.

The case stands otherwise for conversion of carbon monoxide on low-temperature copper catalysts. The reaction does not proceed stepwise, but, instead, requires a simultaneous interaction of both reactants with a catalyst, i.e., follows the concerted mechanism. Carbon monoxide and hydrogen, apparently joined to different copper atoms, are incorporated in the active complex and conversion to the reaction products is accompanied by the electron transition within the catalyst:

In this case, as well as in a stepwise mechanism, carbon monoxide removes oxygen from the catalyst, and water gives it back to the catalyst. These processes proceed simultaneously and are facilitated by electron transition through the catalyst, and their superposition results in a considerable decrease of the energy barrier.

The complete oxidation of hydrocarbons and carbon monoxide with molecular oxygen can serve as the second example of a complicated concerted mechanism. According to IR-data, these reactions proceed through the formation of carbonate and carboxylate groups on the surface of oxide catalysts. Decomposition of these groups with CO_2 evolution

is, in major cases, a relatively slow process determining the oxidation rate by the stage mechanism. At sufficiently high concentrations, the concerted mechanism is possible on the surface of carbonate groups, wherein elimination of CO_2 is combined with the catalyst reoxidation with molecular oxygen. It has been shown that the decomposition rate of carbonate complexes (determined by variations in intensities of the corresponding IR bands and by the output of carbon dioxide) sharply increases in the presence of oxygen in the gas phase. In this case carbonate decomposition and catalyst reoxidation with migration of oxygen and electrons along the catalyst surface go together, and this results in smoothening an energy barrier and increasing the reaction rate.

The complicated concerted mechanism is widely encountered in other fields of catalysis as well. The most detailed studies have been performed on reactions of acid-base catalysis. For example, for the hydration of aldehyde, or addition of alcohol under the influence of phosphate catalysts, a mechanism known as 'push-pull', has been suggested. According to this mechanism, the migration of hydrogen between the individual fragments of reactant molecules occurs in the form of proton-migration through the catalyst and is accompanied by the electron movement in opposite direction. It is a very important fact that the simultaneity and synchronism of these transitions facilitate the progress of the reaction and smoothen the energy barrier as a result of compensation of energy of breaking of old bonds.

A concerted mechanism with conjugation through the catalyst is characteristic of enzymic catalysis. The enzyme active sites and reacting substances form chains or cycles (chains of bond rearrangement) through which a synchronous change of the bond order takes place as a result of proton and electron transition. This causes a high compensation of energy of breaking of old bonds needed for chemical reaction to occur with a small activation energy.

The role of interstage compensation of the first type

An increase in the degree of compensation in catalysis may also be accomplished through interstage compensation of the first type. In many known chain reactions the catalysts aid the formation of species capable of accumulating the energy of reaction and transferring it in the subsequent cycles of the process. The influence of traces of water and water-containing compounds on interaction of carbon monoxide with oxygen offers a classical example of catalyst action. In this case the formation of active species—atoms of hydrogen or hydroxyls—required for carbon monoxide oxidation to occur via a chain path, becomes possible. The phenomenon of excitement of a chain reaction is

especially widespread in the liquid-phase processes of homogeneous catalysis. Thus, in reactions of hydrogen peroxide decomposition, liquid-phase oxidation of organic compounds, polymerization, etc. the introduction of catalyst allows decrease and even complete removal of induction period of the reaction route. In many cases a catalyst directly participates in the propagation of reaction chains.

The role of interstage compensation is less clear in heterogeneous catalysis, although influence of solid surfaces on chain reactions has long been known.

There are detailed data on heterogeneous-homogeneous reactions wherein chains are formed on the surface, and a considerable chemical reaction takes place at the gas-solid and liquid-solid interface.

The most general ideas concerning the nature of heterogeneous catalytic chain reactions were put forward about 20 years ago by Russian school. The possibility of a chain reaction on the surface was attributed by them to the participation of the free valence surface-radicals of solid bodies. However, this concept cannot be admitted as the main, general form of the catalyst action. In fact, a high rate of chain reaction is achieved only when the concentration of active species considerably exceeds the equilibrium value. It cannot be achieved in reaction systems in the state close to equilibrium and in reactions with very small changes of free energy, for example, in reactions of isotopic exchange. At the same time, it has been found that reactions of isotopic exchange proceed at a high rate on catalysts which accelerate chemical transformations of the same substances, and kinetic dependences, and hence the mechanism of most of the reactions of heterogeneous catalysis, do not vary when approaching the equilibrium state. A high activity of most of the reactions of heterogeneous catalysis is not therefore due to the chain route of the process at non-equilibrium concentration of active intermediates. In some cases of heterogeneous catalysis a chain mechanism is not excluded, though there are few experimental supports. Whether a chain mechanism is operative or not, one must take into consideration the possibility of the reaction free energy effect on the catalyst state. It is indicated in the phenomena of the so called 'catalytic corrosion' of metals manifested in dispersion of many metallic catalysts. The appearance of thermodynamically unstable phases, the change of composition and of some properties of solid catalysts in the process of the catalytic reaction, a local accumulation of reaction free energy in the form of excited states of individual sites on the surface or their chemical variations, is also possible. The luminescence observed during some reactions of heterogeneous catalysis and promotion of the catalytic activity give indication of this fact. For example, catalyzing the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide

on manganese oxide catalysts, the catalyst stationary state corresponds to the phase Mn_2O_4 , independent of the catalyst initial state, with disturbed parameters of the crystalline lattice in the next-to-surface layer.

Conclusion

In the heterogeneous catalysis, as well as in other forms of catalysis, the acceleration in the rate of chemical reaction is mainly the result of an increase in the degree of compensation caused by the introduction of catalyst into the reaction active complex.

Interstage compensation of the first type via the chain mechanism is, apparently, very rare in heterogeneous catalysis.

Increasing the compensation energy of bond breaking in reactions of heterogeneous catalysis is achieved mainly by the complicated interaction of reactants with a catalyst, i.e., via :

- i) the mechanism of an intermediate stepwise interaction of reactants with a catalyst leading to the reaction proceeding through a series of stages, and
- ii) the mechanism of a concerted (associative) interaction of reactants with a catalyst with the conjugation of individual elements of chemical conversion through a catalyst.

The difference in mechanisms corresponds to the difference in the properties of catalysts incorporated in chemical reactions.

With the first, stepwise mechanism, in the case of decreasing the reaction molecularity, the fall of activation energy may be due to the decrease of the sum of energies of breaking bonds at all stages. However, in this case a high reaction rate can also be achieved through a high compensation degree. According to the available experimental data, when a stepwise mechanism takes place the completeness of compensation is not usually achieved, and activation energies of the catalytic reactions become significant. On the other hand, owing to a small number of species which form an active complex and to the simplicity of its composition, the values of activation entropy and frequency factor are likely to be high. Thus, values of the binding energy of reactants with a catalyst are of prime importance in predicting the catalytic activity. Due to the change in the catalyst composition at the consecutive reaction stages, its stationary composition and surface structure are quickly established, and a specific catalytic activity of catalysts of similar composition is approximately the same.

Increasing the compensation degree during the second, concerted mechanism, is achieved by the

conjugation of individual reaction elements through a catalyst. In many cases a catalytic reaction can be carried out at a very low, close to zero, activation energy. At the same time, the entropy of the active complex and, correspondingly, the frequency factor, have low values because reactants and the catalyst must be combined in an active complex with very strict mutual orientation. The catalyst composition in the elementary acts of chemical conversion at the concerted mechanism does not vary and, therefore, a catalyst stationary state is attained very slowly; also, the specific activity of the catalyst can vary over a wide range depending on the catalyst preparation and pretreatment conditions. Catalysts for

reactions proceeding via the concerted mechanism are more complicated systems since the conjugation of individual elements requires a certain combination of active centers with a possibility of electron transition between them.

A survey of the existing data shows that most of the commercial catalytic processes proceed via stepwise mechanism, whereas concerted mechanism includes wide ranges of liquid-phase and enzyme catalysis. Further investigations into this, I believe, will lead to development of newer, effective catalysts for carrying out reactions at comparatively lower temperatures.